

Adaptation of DIGCOMEDU for Early Childhood Education

Area	Competence	Descriptor
1. Professional engagement	1.1 Organizational communication	Use digital technologies to improve organizational communication with training partners, professional teams linked to the practice and children's families.
	1.2 Professional collaboration	Explore the possibilities of digital technologies to develop collaborative experiences with fellow students and professional teams linked to the practice, to share and exchange knowledge, experiences and innovate pedagogical practices together.
	1.3 Reflexive practice	Reflect on one's own and others' digital pedagogical practice.
	1.4 Continuing Professional Development (CPD) through digital media.	Identify sources of information to improve their knowledge on the use of digital technologies in their professional teacher training.
2. Resources	2.1 Selection of digital resources	Locate, use and evaluate digital resources for teaching and learning considering learning objectives, context, pedagogical approach and educational level.
	2.2 Creating and modifying digital resources	Create, modify and/or adapt digital resources, individually and collectively, based on the learning objectives, context, methodology and educational level.
	2.3 Protection, management and sharing resources	Select and organize resources in order to make them available for use and review by training partners, children, family and professionals of the practice centers, knowing the use of free licenses, including their correct reference.
3. Teaching and Learning	3.1 Teaching	Plan the use of digital devices and resources in the teaching-learning process, in order to improve their pedagogical interventions through methodologies that favor an active role of girls and boys.
	3.2 Orientation and support in learning	Use digital technologies to improve individual and collective interaction with the family of children, in order to offer relevant and specific guidance and support.
	3.3 Collaborative learning	Use technologies to develop and encourage children to work collaboratively in order to facilitate communication, cooperation and learning.
	3.4 Self-regulated learning	Use digital technologies to favor self-regulation processes of children.

4. Assessment and feedback	4.1 Assessment strategies	Use digital technologies for the process of diagnosing, monitoring and providing feedback on children's achievements and communicating them efficiently and effectively to families.
	4.2 Learning analytics	Use digital technologies to analyze and interpret, in a critical way, the evaluation results for decision making in the planning of the teaching and learning process.
	4.3 Feedback, programming and decision making	Use digital technologies to process data derived from learning progress and provide specific feedback.
5. Student empowerment	5.1 Accessibly and inclusion	Recognize elements that facilitate accessibility for girls and boys, including those with special educational needs, in pedagogical learning resources and experiences.
	5.2 Personalization	Use digital technologies to meet the diverse learning needs of girls and boys, allowing them to advance at their learning pace.
	5.3 Active engagement of students with their own learning	Use digital technologies to promote children's interest in learning experiences.
6. Development of students' digital competence	6.1 Information and media literacy	Encourage the use of digital technologies in the search for information by children with the support of their families.
	6.2 Digital communication and collaboration	Incorporate learning experiences with digital resources, tasks and games that require children to know rules of use and respect for the work of their peers, for communication and digital collaboration.
	6.3 Resources creation	Include learning experiences that require children to express themselves using digital technologies.
	6.4 Responsible use	Adopt measures to ensure the physical, psychological and social well-being of children when using digital technologies.
	6.5 Digital problem solving	Incorporate learning experiences that require children to identify and solve simple technical problems derived from the use of digital technologies.